

Structural and Optical Characterization of Manganese Oxalate Crystals Grown by Agar -Agar Gel Method

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Abstract– Single crystal of manganese oxalate crystals was grown by using agar – agar gel method at room temperature. Effect of different parameters on the growth of manganese crystals has been studied and reported. X- ray Diffraction study indicates that the prepared grown crystal confirmed the crystal structure. X-ray diffraction measurement displayed crystallization in monoclinic crystal system. Fourier Transforms Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) investigated that the presence of oxalate ligands, metal- oxygen bonds and crystallization of water molecule within manganese oxalate. Scanning Electron Microscope images highlights that crystals were grown by layer deposition.

Keywords – Gel method, XRD, FTIR, SEM, PL.

I. INTRODUCTION

Crystal growth is the basis of many technologies. Crystal growth is an important part of modern society. Thus, crystal growth must be controlled by the crystallisation process in industry. Crystal growth in the principle involves the control of phase change. Vapour phase, gel growth, solution growth, and melt growth these are various method for crystal growth [1]. Material required high purity as well as high degree of perfection in crystalline structure with minimum defect. The growth of single crystal in laboratory comprises two distinct step 1) Nucleation 2) The growth of crystal [2]. Crystal of different shapes are found in nature. The size of these crystals depends on the type of intermolecular bonds as well as the conditions under which they were formed [3]. The single crystals are the backbone of modern technology. The effect of single crystal in high demand in industries such as ceramics, physics, chemistry, metallurgy, mineralogy, medicine, engineering, [4] amplifiers, semiconductor, optics, piezoelectric, photosensitive material, infrared, nonlinear optics, microelectronic and microprocessor [5]. The single crystal also used as display permeant magnet [6] and optics [7]. The single crystal of these material cannot grow either by slow solvent evaporation or melting techniques due to oxalate crystals being insoluble in water [8] and prior to decomposition to melt. Crystal growth in gel is superior and simple technique for growing single crystal for metal oxalate [9] and transition metal oxalate [10] due to their solubility in water [11]. Gel technique is most efficient and simplest process for growing single crystal. The principle used in this crystal growth technique is very simple solution of two compound which give rise to the required insoluble crystalline substance by chemical reaction between them are allowed to diffuse into gel medium chemically reacts, thus gel method is capable for to achieved good quality crystal of high optical perfection. Among different method of growing single crystal, gel method occupies prominent place owing to its versatility and simplicity. The gel method is simple, low cost as well as not ph dependent. Crystal can grow at room temperature so many research had selected gel method for crystal growth. The rare earth mixed oxalate and molybdate crystals are grown by gel method at ambient temperature and characterized using serval techniques [12]. Many researchers use silica gel to single grown crystals [13-17] while very few researchers used agar-agar gel to grown single crystals [18-20]. Manganese oxalate grown has been reported mainly with silica gel [21-23] and manganese oxalate crystal growth in agar-agar gel has been rarely studied [24]. Manganese oxalate crystal shows a significant effect on a paint as well as textiles. Manganese oxalate crystal used as semiconductor, photosensitive material. Thus, we reported and discuss in the present paper the growth and characterization of manganese oxalate crystal growth in agar- agar gel using single diffusion method.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The single gel diffusion method is used to synthesize manganese oxalate. Manganese chloride (MnCl_2), Oxalic acid ($\text{H}_2\text{C}_2\text{O}_4$) and agar-agar powder is used as chemical compound. All these chemical compounds were AR grade. The solutions have prepared by distilled water at constant string and kept in dark and cool place. Single class tube having 15 cm and 2.5 diameter were filled by manganese chloride of desired volume and molarity. The hot agar-agar solution was poured to the tube containing manganese chloride. The homogenous solution kept for setting gel at room temperature in dust free atmosphere. Aqueous solution of oxalic acid with desire volume and molarity transfers into set gel along the wall of test tube. After 8-week nucleation process was completed and good quality crystals having average size $2 \times 1 \times 1 \text{ mm}^3$ were obtained. Growth of manganese oxalate in the test tube as shown in figure1 and the grown manganese oxalate crystals having different shapes like as spherical, blocky, granular, crumb shape were observed. Different morphology of grown manganese oxalate crystals are shown in figure 2. The following reaction is expected to take place giving required compound.

Fig.1. Growth of manganese oxalate crystal in test tube

Fig. 2. Different morphology harvest manganese oxalate crystals

III. CHARACTERIZATION

A. X-RAY DIFFRACTOMETER (XRD)

Fig 3. XRD pattern of the grown manganese oxalate crystals

2θ	d value	Relative Intensity (cts)	FWHM	Indices
18.373	4.8250	6609.01	0.100 ⁰	-2 0 1
18.834	4.7079	8217.22	0.100 ⁰	2 0 0
22.669	3.9193	900.012	0.100 ⁰	0 0 2
24.458	3.6366	622.857	0.100 ⁰	1 1 1
29.770	2.9986	2900.83	0.100 ⁰	-4 0 2
33.342	2.6851	642.737	0.153 ⁰	1 1 -3
39.277	2.2920	255.974	0.100 ⁰	0 0 2
44.321	2.04216	213.338	0.100 ⁰	1 1 3
46.601	1.9473	438.512	0.100 ⁰	-4 2 1
47.365	1.9177	450.902	0.117 ⁰	0 2 3
49.306	1.8466	292.513	0.100 ⁰	-1 3 1
49.938	1.8248	167.386	0.246 ⁰	-4 2 4

Table 1. XRD data of grown manganese oxalate crystal

The x-ray diffraction (XRD) is used to determine crystal structure of unknown materials. X- ray pattern of manganese oxalate crystal is as shown in figure 3. The powder sample of manganese oxalate crystal was subjected to x-ray diffraction analysis using with characteristic cu ka (1.5406 \AA) radiation which carried out at CRYSTA PEAK SOLUTION LAB, Pune. The Sample scanned in the 2θ value in the region between 10° to 70° . The 2θ value, d value, FWHM value, relative intensity, and miller indices (h k l) of major peak observed in spectra of manganese oxalate crystal are issued in the table 1. The characteristic peak appears at $18.83 (2\theta)$. The XRD pattern investigated that the given sample is crystalline in the nature having monocline structure. These results are well agreement with the stander JCPDS data card no (25-0544). The grain size of grown crystal was $D = 84.14 \text{ nm}$ calculated using x- ray direction line broadening analysis based on the Scherer's formula. The breadth of direction line was determined by the full width at half maximum (FWHM). The lattice parameter from XRD data was observed that $a = 12.016$, $b = 5.632$, $c = 9.961$, $\alpha = 90^\circ$, $\beta = 128.4^\circ$, $\gamma = 90^\circ$ and unit cell volume $V = 528.29 \text{ \AA}^3$. In monoclinic crystal system the lengths of unit cell are different i.e. $a \neq b \neq c$ and $\alpha = \gamma \neq \beta$. The crystal parameters of manganese oxalate crystal are shown in table 2.

Crystal Parameter	a \AA	b \AA	c \AA	α°	β°	γ°	volume \AA^3
Manganese Oxalate	12.016	5.632	9.9610	90	128.4	90	508.29

Table 2. Crystal lattice parameter of grown manganese oxalate crystal

B. FOURIER TRANSFORMS INFRARED SPECTROSCOPY (FTIR)

Fig 4. FTIR spectrum of the grown manganese oxalate crystals

Fourier Transforms Infrared Spectroscopic (FTIR) technique is used to measure functional group in compound [25-26]. The transmittance spectrum of manganese oxalate crystal had been analysed using Fourier Transforms Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR). Spectrum. The FTIR spectra of manganese oxalate crystals were recorded in the region 4000 cm^{-1} to 400 cm^{-1} by using KBr pellet technique Shimadzu FTIR – 8400S spectrometer which is carried out at R. C. Patel Pharmacy Research Institute, Shirpur. The FTIR spectrum of manganese oxalate crystals are shown in figure 4. The fundamental vibration frequencies observed in grown crystals [27]. The bond assigned to different type of vibration are tabulated in table 3. The spectrum shows the peak in the range 3500 cm^{-1} to 500 cm^{-1} . The bond 3371.37 , 3339.91 implies the symmetric and asymmetric O-H strong stretching of water molecule. The wave number at 1614.24 cm^{-1} corresponding to C-C stretching. The presence of C-O stretching group is indicated by occurrence the sharp and intense bond 1360.40 cm^{-1} [28-29]. The bond at 812.22 cm^{-1} attributed C-H bending bond. The metal oxygen stretching bond observed below 725.53 cm^{-1} .

Sr. No	Wave Number cm^{-1}	Assignments
1.	3377.69, 3334.44	O-H stretching and water molecule
2.	1618.37	C-C stretching
3.	1313.91	C-O stretching
4.	813.12	C-H stretching
5.	720.36	Metal oxygen bond

Table 3. FTIR data of grown cadmium manganese oxalate crystals

C. SCANNING ELECTRON MICROSCOPE (SEM)

Scanning electron microscope (SEM) is utilized to study of the grown crystals. The SEM images use to check the presence of imperfection also used to identified information about internal structure of crystal. In the present work powder sample of manganese oxalate crystals were investigation by scanning electron microscope (SEM) which is carried out at PEAK SOLUTON LAB, Pune. The SEM photograph of manganese oxalate crystals as shown in figure 5. It is observed that manganese oxalate crystals had composed of many sheets approximately greeter than 276.8 nm in length. SEM images of manganese oxalate show a coarse mixture of compound of different particle size. The grown manganese oxalate crystal is predominantly crystalline and characterized by the formation of various shape with regular phases. The SEM images show crystal growth by depositing layers including rectangular, pentagonal, cubic, rod, square, quadrilateral, diamond, capsulated, conical, spherical, elliptical, flat, coiled, cocci triangular, selenite, orthorhombic etc. shapes are visible in SEM photograph [30-31]. SEM image in figure 5 (a) shows pieces of camphor. In the figure 5(d) crystal growth like as lichen and crushed of samosa as shown in figure 5 (e).

Fig. 5. Various SEM photograph of grown manganese oxalate crystal

D. PHOTOLUMINESCENCE SPECTROSCOPY (PL)

Photoluminescence Spectroscopy (PL) is used to observe material imperfections and impurities. The powder sample of manganese oxalate crystals were observed by Photoluminescence Spectroscopy (PL) which is carried out at PEAK SOLUTON LAB, Pune. Figure 6 shows the photoluminescence Spectrum of manganese oxalate crystals was recorded at room temperature. The emission spectrum shows the peaks mainly at 411nm, 510 nm, 605 nm and 710 nm when excited with 391 nm. Most intense peak is at 411 nm which is the violet emission and which have given photon energy in the range 2.75- 3.26 [32]. The green emission at 510 nm is less intense. The orange emission observed at 605 nm and red emission at 710 nm [33]. It can be seen the grown manganese oxalate crystals are having the fluorescent property.

Fig. 6. Emission spectrum of grown manganese oxalate crystal

IV. Conclusion

Single crystal of manganese oxalate crystals was successfully grown by using single diffusion technique in agar-agar gel method at room temperature. White colour with average size of $2 \times 1 \times 1 \text{ mm}^3$ were obtained during a period near about 2 months at room temperature by applying different parameter. X-ray diffractometer measure that grown crystal are in crystalline in nature and having monoclinic structure. Fourier Transforms Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) identified that manganese oxalate reveals the presence of oxalate ligands (C-C, C-O,) and crystallization water molecule (C-H). SEM images suggest that grown crystal has different morphology like as rectangular, pentagonal, cubic, rod, square, quadrilateral, diamond, capsulated, conical, triangular, spherical, and pyramidal shape. Manganese oxalate crystals investigated the visible, green, orange, red emission

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